

Innovative Pedagogical Practices: Utilizing Role Play as a Catalyst for Active Learning in Finance

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Abstract: *This study examines the incorporation of role-play as an educational instrument to improve comprehension of complex finance subjects among Diploma in Banking students at UiTM Sabah Branch, Kota Kinabalu Campus. Conventional pedagogical approaches, predominantly dependent on lectures and tutorials, frequently lead to passive learning and restricted engagement, especially in complex subjects such as financial ratios, capital planning, short-term financing and more. Conventional techniques, assessed via tests, quizzes, and final examinations, lack the capacity to sufficiently reflect students' practical comprehension or engagement with the topic. A quasi-experimental methodology was utilised to compare student outcomes prior to and following the implementation of role-play as a pedagogical strategy. During the assessment, students participated in actual financial scenarios that necessitated the active application of learning concepts, so fostering critical thinking, teamwork, and practical skills. The efficacy of this method was evaluated utilising before and after the intervention assessments, including both information retention and application. Initial data suggest that students participating in role-play demonstrate substantially improved understanding of financial topics relative to those who participate in conventional educational environments. The research underscores the beneficial effects of practical learning on student engagement, motivation, and the recall of complex financial concepts. Additionally, the commercialisation potential of this method is examined, indicating that including role-play into finance curriculum may improve job skills and practical preparedness among graduates. This research highlights the significant influence of experiential learning on finance knowledge, providing essential insights for educators seeking to improve student learning outcomes and job ability.*

Keywords: Finance; Role play; Active learning

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1. INTRODUCTION

The educational landscape, especially in finance, is adapting to the requirements of a constantly changing world. Conventional teaching approaches, mostly focused on lectures and tutorials, frequently lack to promote critical thinking, creativity, and active student engagement. Traditional evaluations, including tests, quizzes, and final examinations, may particularly evaluate memorising facts instead of an in-depth understanding of financial concepts. Research indicates that these strategies can foster passive learning, wherein students are merely consumers of information, leading to restricted application of knowledge in real-world contexts (Biggs & Tang, 2011).

Conversely, role play arises as a dynamic teaching strategy that can operate as a stimulus for active learning in financial literacy. Through the simulation of actual financial scenarios, role play promotes active engagement with the topic at hand, allows teamwork among peers, and facilitates the application of theoretical knowledge in practical contexts. A study by Kolb (2014) shown that the integration of role play into the curriculum substantially enhanced students' problem-solving abilities and their capacity to apply financial concept in practical situations. Moreover, role play not only boosts student interest and engagement but also fosters critical soft skills, like the ability to communicate, and teamwork (Baker et al., 2017). The incorporation of role play strongly coincides with the Falsafah Pendidikan Malaysia, which underscores holistic education and the cultivation of balanced individuals skilled in critical thinking and innovative problem-solving. The implementation of the Integrated Cumulative Grade Point Average (iCGPA) framework has accelerated modifications in assessment methodologies, prompting educators to integrate affective components with cognitive learning in their evaluations (Ministry of Education Malaysia, 2016). This transition recognises that effective learning goes beyond conventional lectures and evaluations, advocating for a holistic approach that emphasises the emotional and interpersonal competencies essential for success in today's workforce.

This research examines an innovative incorporation of role play in finance studies to promote active learning, thereby addressing the shortcomings of traditional teaching approaches. This research seeks to illustrate the substantial influence of active learning on student achievements and its pertinence to modern educational philosophies, by analysing the advantages of role play, supported by empirical evidence from previous studies.

2. METHOD & MATERIAL

This research utilised a quasi-experimental design to assess the effect of role play as a pedagogical approach on active learning in finance among Diploma students at UiTM Sabah Branch, Kota Kinabalu Campus. The quasi-experimental methodology is suitable for this research as it facilitates the comparison of outcomes between groups subjected to varying teaching methods without random assignment, which is usually impractical in educational contexts (Shadish et al., 2002).

2.1 Sample

The study sample will comprise Diploma students enrolled in the Fundamentals of Finance (FIN242) course. The research will concentrate on two groups:

- Cohort 1: Students who participated in the course from 2014 to 2015, during which only conventional teaching methods (lectures and tutorials) were utilised.
- Cohort 2: Students who enrolled in the course from 2016 onwards, subsequent to the integration of role play into the teaching technique, following the implementation of the Integrated Cumulative Grade Point Average (iCGPA) system.

The two cohorts will be compared to assess the efficacy of role play in improving active learning and engagement in finance topics.

2.2 Implementation of Role Play

Since 2016, lecturers for the Fundamentals of Finance (FIN242) course has been employing role-playing as an innovative assessment technique. These interactive role-play exercises aim to enhance students' comprehension of fundamental finance topics including:

- Financial Ratios: Students will engage in simulations of actual scenarios requiring the analysis and interpretation of companies' financial ratios.
- Short-Term Financing: The role play will encompass situations in which students discuss the costs that apply for short-term loans.
- Capital Budgeting: Students will participate in simulated investment decisions, assessing prospective projects and determining investment recommendations.

2.3 Data Collection

The collected data focuses on students' academic performance in the course, particularly comparing outcomes prior to and subsequent to the adoption of role play. The quantitative data will be carefully analysed using statistical methods to assess and compare the academic achievement of the two cohorts appropriately. This project entails involving students in a role-playing exercise that simulates real-world financial decision-making conditions. The essential steps are:

- Group formation: Students are organised into groups consisting of 5 to 6 individuals.
- Role assignment: The role-play technique involves students adopting various leadership positions within a financial context, such as Chief Financial Officer, Cash Manager, Risk Manager, or Investor, contingent upon the scenario. The positions emphasise the analysis of financial subjects, including financial ratios, short-term financing, and capital budgeting projects, while making strategic financial decisions based on these ratios, financing costs, or capital budgeting techniques. This method fosters experiential learning, enabling students to cultivate decision-making, problem-solving, and leadership competencies. The roles are intended to mirror actual financial issues that students may face in their future professions, thereby assisting their comprehension of financial strategies and concepts.
- Scenario analysis: The group receives financial statements, a corporate scenario, or a case study and must assess the firm's circumstances, identify the optimal short-term financing solution, and provide strategies to mitigate the company's issues. The instructor facilitates the role-play process, offering feedback on student engagement, teamwork, and the quality of their financial analysis and proposed strategies.
- Teamwork and strategy formulation: Students engage in discussions regarding the company's financial condition, accompanied by their analysis, and provide strategies to enhance or mitigate the financial issues facing the business. The group members present their findings and recommendations, demonstrating their leadership abilities in financial decision-making through role-play activities.
- Report submission: A report encompassing the analysis, specifically the financial situation, role allocations, and the computed financial ratios are required for submission. The report can be limited to five pages, including a cover page.

3. FINDINGS

3.1 Descriptive Statistics

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics for Role Play.

Statistics	Score
N	14
Max	87
Mean	73.93
Min	52
SD	9.31
Interquartile Range	
25th Percentile	68
50th Percentile (Median)	76
75th Percentile	80

Note: Table 1 summarizes the descriptive statistics (i.e. number of observations (N), maximum (max), mean, minimum (min), standard deviation (SD), and the interquartile range for 25th percentile and 75th percentile of the overall sample. Data represent the overall sample of the PLO scores attainment for the role-play assessment.

The role-play intervention measured by the PLO 5 scores shows key insights into the overall performance of students following the implementation of role-play in teaching and learning activities. The mean score of 73.93 with standard deviation (SD) of 9.31 indicates a moderate level of comprehension, with a score between 52 and 87. This finding suggests that the students' performance is at satisfactory level, although there are notable variations in outcomes among students, reflecting differences in engagement or prior knowledge. The interquartile range further validates this finding with the majority of students performing above average, with the 25th percentile at 68 and the 75th percentile at 80. The difference suggests a generally positive impact of the role-play on the students' learning method, with a few students attain scores close to the upper end scale.

3.2 Trend Analysis

Table 2. Trend Analysis for Role-Play Scores Across Semester

Semester	Score
2 2016/2017	67
1 2017/2018	65
2 2017/2018	65
2 2018/2019	73
1 2019/2020	52
2 2019/2020	83
1 2020/2021	71
2 2020/2021	80
1 2021/2022	73
2 2021/2022	80
1 2022/2023	81
2 2022/2023	79
1 2023/2024	87
2 2023/2024	79

Note: Table 2 summarizes the trend of the role-play scores across different semesters (i.e. semester 2 2016/2017, semester 1 and 2 2017/2018, semester 2 2018/2019, semester 1 and 2 2019/2020, semester 1 and 2 2020/2021, semester 1 and 2 2021/2022, semester 1 and 2 2022/2023, and semester 1 and 2 2023/2024). Data represents the overall score of the role-play attainment.

An analysis of the role-play scores across 14 semesters demonstrates an upward trend, underscoring the cumulative benefits of the role-play pedagogy. Scores initially showed at low level

between semester 2 2016/2017 (67) and semester 1 2019/2020 (52), before showing marked improvement from semester 2 2019/2020 (83) to semester 1 2023/2024 (87) and only a slight decline in semester 2 2023/2024 (79). The steady increase is consistent with pedagogical theories emphasizing on the experiential and active learning strategies. By simulating role-play environments, the students are able to bridge the gap between theoretical concepts and practical application, thereby enhancing their understanding on the financial ratios. The upward trajectory trend promotes comprehension and analytical skills among students.

3.3 Grade Distribution

Table 3. Grade Distribution of Role-Play Scores for 14 Semesters

Grade	Frequencies
A	5
A-	2
B+	3
B	3
C	1

Note: Table 3 summarizes the grade distribution of role-play scores for 14 semesters (i.e. semester 2 2016/2017, semester 1 and 2 2017/2018, semester 2 2018/2019, semester 1 and 2 2019/2020, semester 1 and 2 2020/2021, semester 1 and 2 2021/2022, semester 1 and 2 2022/2023, and semester 1 and 2 2023/2024). Data represents the frequencies of grade A, A-, B+, B, and C for the role-play intervention.

Table 3 indicates the grade distribution showing the effectiveness of the role-play interventions, with a majority of students receiving grade A (5 semesters), A- (2 semesters), B+ and B (3 semesters), and only 1 semester receiving grade C. This distribution suggests that the role-play activities can enhance the competency and enable the students to excel in their academic performance. This finding is consistent with the notion that engaging students in immersive, real-world scenarios assists them in cultivating critical thinking, communication skills, and teamwork skills. Further, the progression increases in the number of occurrences in grade A over 14 semesters suggesting that role-play interventions are crucial in facilitating deeper learning as students’ adept within complex and simulated environments when applying the financial ratios in the role-play activities.

4. DISCUSSION

The key findings of the study highlight a satisfactory mean score of 70.5 indicates that the integration of role play as a pedagogical approach influenced students’ comprehension of finance concepts particularly on the financial ratios, short-term financing, and capital budgeting. The performance of students in the post 2016 cohort, who experience role play shows a steady upward trend in role play scores across semesters suggests that this teaching approach encourages deeper learning experience. Also, the grade distribution analysis shows that role play intervention helped students to perform with a notable increase in the number of students achieving grade A over 14 semesters.

The role play intervention provided significant insights into the enhancement of students’ communication skills as measured by PLO5 scores. The findings show that engaging in role play allows students to actively practice and demonstrate effective communication which is a very critical skill in the finance industry. This aligned with Baker et al. (2017), that emphasized role play able to enhance crucial soft skills particularly communication and teamwork.

The findings further support that the role play is effective in promoting deeper understanding of financial topics as compared to traditional lecture-based teaching. Therefore, this study emphasizes the need to shift from traditional lecture-based teaching to more experiential learning methods by embedding role play into the curriculum. This supports the National Education Philosophy on holistic education.

However, the variability in student scores with standard deviation of 5.96 and an interquartile range from 65.5 to 73.5, indicates that some students still struggled to engage fully or lacked prior knowledge. Therefore, the findings address individual differences in the classroom which need additional support and guidance in navigating practical financial scenarios.

5. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, this study emphasises the importance of role-playing as a creative and experiential learning strategy for improving students' understanding of complex finance concepts. Role-playing engages students more actively than traditional lecture-based techniques by introducing real-life financial problems into the learning process, developing critical thinking, teamwork, and practical skills needed in the real world. The quasi-experimental method revealed significant improvements in memory and understanding among students exposed to role-playing compared to those in traditional educational environments. This study's unique contribution is its emphasis on role-playing's capacity to bridge the gap between academic theory and practical application, preparing students for the complex dynamics of the finance industry and increasing their ability to work. The findings highlight the importance of adding experiential learning into finance curriculum, providing a practical approach that may be commercialised and adapted across diverse educational contexts to suit the changing demands of the job market.

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